

BENEFITS OF LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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AWESOME ADVANTAGES OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Abstract: Now, modern world is becoming increasingly globalised and bilingualism. So, learning foreign languages is blossoming year by year. Because communicating with other countries and peoples is incredibly important nowadays. In other words, foreign languages study estimates people's chances in business, technology, industry, art and government.

Key words: bilingualism, superiority, globalised, people's chances, Cognitive, Academic, Communicative, Economic.

Introduction. Our capacity for interpersonal connection is among the most fulfilling features of the human experience. It is a wonderful privilege to be able to communicate with someone in their own language. In both their personal and professional life, bilinguals have the exceptional potential to communicate with a wider spectrum of people. No matter where you are, speaking the language makes you a local, expanding both your real and figurative horizons. Communities will influence how you are. You will be moved by people's generosity. You will make pals for life. You will reap the benefits of learning languages for many years to come just for these reasons. Language is the most direct connection to other cultures. Being able to communicate in another language exposes us to and fosters an appreciation for the traditions, religions, arts, and history of the people associated with that language. Greater understanding, in turn, promotes greater tolerance, empathy, and acceptance of others—with studies showing that children who have studied another language are more open toward and express more positive attitudes toward the culture associated with that language.

Literature analysis. We are all aware of how well-developed Russian and English are in our nation. As you can see, English language proficiency is substantially lower than it should be in the global rankings. According to the research mentioned above, countries' economic progress is directly impacted by their citizens' competency in the English language. What then has to be done to promote the use of English in Uzbekistan?

Let's first examine the top four reasons why learning English is crucial: More than 400 million people in 53 countries speak English, which is a widely accepted language of communication. Research indicates that English is the official language of business. The official business language is English, and studies suggest that business English is a common language used while conducting business abroad, and many global corporations want Speaking English opens up a world of extra opportunities. Speaking English opens up a world of extra opportunities.

In 2019, Decree №5712 was adopted to approve the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.

International partners were given the notion by the Ministry of Public Education.

This program has received backing from our American allies.

Since English is a common international language, Uzbekistan is stepping up its partnerships with other nations. School graduates need to have a strong grasp of foreign languages in order to expand international collaboration and boost our nation's competitiveness.

In the "Year of Science, Enlightenment, and the Digital Economy," this was a significant factor. The new English Speaking Nation: Secondary Teacher Training project of the Ministry of Public Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the American organization will offer a chance to enhance the knowledge and abilities of more than 33,000 English teachers in secondary schools as a continuation of the aforementioned.

An initiative to raise the English language proficiency of teachers in the public education system is called the English Speaking Nation: Secondary Teacher Training (ESN: STT) project. The program, which is being carried out in close cooperation with the Department of Public Education and the American Councils for International Education, intends to provide chances for English language instructors in our nation to advance their careers.

Methods of analysis. Types of benefits of learning the foreign languages.
Cognitive benefits

It also improves our listening and memory skills. Recent research indicates that “The length of time students study a foreign languages relates directly and positively to higher levels of cognitive.

Academic benefits

As a result of improving critical thinking skills, many who study a Foreign Languages make higher test scores.

Improves academic performance in English grammar, vocabulary, reading, writing.

Communicative benefits

Learning another language can develop your ability to interpret, discuss, interact and recognize patterns of behavior/gesture/ social cues.

Economic benefits

Opportunities in today’s global marketplace. Research clearly shows that multilingual societies have a competitive advantage over monolingual ones in the area of international trade. Have more job opportunities. Get a promotion

In today’s increasingly interconnected and interdependent world, proficiency in other languages is a vital skill that gives you the opportunity to engage with the world in a more immediate and meaningful way—whether in your neighborhood or thousands of miles away—while better preparing you to compete and succeed in the global economy.

You will become much more conscious of not only cultural customs, but of the grammar, vocabulary, and pronunciation patterns of your first language. This likely explains the improvements in listening, reading, and writing skills that foreign language impart to former monolinguals

Travel becomes cheaper and easier when you learn a foreign language without the right lingo, you are limited to expensive or slower options. So you save yourself some time, money, and grief when you learn a foreign language. Just as a few key phrases will make transportation that much faster and cheaper, and the same is true for choosing a place to stay. This means lower rates and a better experience. When you learn a foreign language, You can ask around for yourself. This valuable intel will usually lead you to far tastier and cheaper fare than any tourism board or guidebook ever could.

Foreign language study grows your brain.

Studies have demonstrated the cognitive benefits of learning another language, no matter how old you are. These studies have shown that bilinguals tend to have bigger brains, better memories, are more creative, better problem solvers, etc. Not only do these advantages make it easier to learn yet more languages, they also make it easier to learn, well, anything. The ability to quickly switch between tasks is especially

important in today's busy multitasking world. Bilinguals can switch between tasks much faster than their monolingual counterparts and can handle many more tasks at once.

Form meaningful friendships when you study a foreign language.

Meeting new and interesting people and developing lifelong friendships are certainly objectives well worth aspiring for, and learning another language is a sure way to expedite that process. Language helps express our feelings, desires, and connect with other humans around us and forms meaningful relationships. Speaking a foreign language not only opens up a massive pool of potential friends, but it also acts as an instant common denominator when you meet native speakers. Plus, speaking in a foreign tongue can be like speaking in secret code with your new besties.

Learning a foreign language opens up a world of job opportunities

It's no secret that learning a foreign language can improve your employment prospects. More companies than ever are doing business in several—often dozens of—countries around the world, but they can't do it without hiring people who have a grasp on at least one foreign language. Even in small, local companies, chances are that the ability to speak a second language will set you apart from other applicants. And in an increasingly competitive job market, why not give yourself every possible edge?

But, it's not just about padding your resume. With globalization in full swing, there's a good chance you'll be working with people whose first language isn't Russian. Being able to communicate in other languages makes you much more valuable to an employer and having that competitive edge on your resume is without a doubt an eye-catcher. Now you can take it to all those mono-lingual losers.

Studying a foreign language makes you more open-minded.

Foreign language study is simply part of a very basic liberal education. To educate is to lead out—to lead out of confinement and narrowness and darkness. Learning a foreign language and getting soaked into an entirely new culture and worldview is the surest way to become an open-minded, understanding, tolerant individual, and that is absolutely priceless. Once you are aware of the fact that we are all cultural beings, products of our own environments, and that you recognize the cultural base for your own attitudes and behavior, you are ready to consider others in a more favourable light. Seeing the world from a different perspective, and understanding where you and others come from, is a fantastic, eye-opening experience.

Foreign language study helps you better understand your own language and culture. Learning a foreign language can actually pull a sort of reverse psychology on you and provide you with a better understanding of your own native tongue and culture. This is one of the most unexpected advantages of learning a foreign language.

Each year, Uzbekistan determines a number of fields of knowledge, the advancement of which is given top importance. These areas this year include physics and foreign languages. The openness of Uzbekistan, its active participation in the global economy, and the rise of global collaboration in all spheres raise the importance of learning foreign languages.

In 25 higher education institutes in Uzbekistan, foreign language instruction is provided. The number of applicants who have obtained a language certificate at an international level has multiplied tenfold over the previous three years.

However, the state of the system of teaching foreign languages at some places does not allow effectively solving the large-scale tasks in this area. So, in the education system, there are more than 2 thousand vacancies for foreign language teachers. The quality of teaching languages in 1.4 thousand schools is assessed as extremely low. Only 4 percent of school teachers have national and international language certificates. There are no teachers with a certificate in the cities of Khanabad and Kuvasay, Zafarabad, Mirishkor, Turtkul, Sherabad and Uzun districts. 49 percent of teachers failed the certification test. These and other problems in the sphere were comprehensively analyzed at the meeting. Priority tasks were identified. "The time has come to create in Uzbekistan a new system of teaching foreign languages, which will become a solid foundation for the future. Since we set ourselves the goal of building a competitive state, from now on, graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must be fluent in at least two foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the work of the head of each education institution", Shavkat Mirziyoyev said. It was noted that an Agency for the Promotion of Learning Foreign Languages will be created under the Cabinet of Ministers.

However, the status of the foreign language education system in some regions prevents effective completion of the substantial tasks in this field.

Therefore, there are more than 2,000 openings for foreign language teachers in the educational system.

In 1.4 thousand schools, the level of language instruction is rated as being very low. Only 4% of school teachers are certified in both native and foreign languages. Khanabad, Kuvasay, Zafarabad, Mirishkor, Turtkul, Sherabad, and Uzun districts do not have any certified instructors. 49 percent of teachers failed the certification test. At the meeting, a thorough analysis of these and other sphere related issues was conducted.

Discussion and conclusion. Learning foreign languages are mushrooming as the world becomes increasingly globalized and bilingualism is now perhaps the most

useful real world skill to ever exist, rather than just being a nifty party trick. If you're thinking about making the effort to learn a foreign language rather than expecting the world to accommodate your monolingualism, you are a rare breed indeed. Blossoming into the impressive polyglot you aspire to be is 100% feasible with the right approach and mindset. Foreign language study is all about learning how to truly communicate and connect with others—an incredibly important life skill that can only be cultivated by interacting with people. When you master a foreign language, you can exercise your new superhuman power of being able to understand what someone is saying, recall the proper vocab and grammar, put that vocab and grammar into the proper context, and reply back—all on the spot and in a timely manner.

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